

PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL OF WORK IMMERSION STUDENTS IN ARTACHO NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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Performance Appraisal of Work Immersion Students in Artacho National High School

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the students who are participating in work immersion at Artacho National High School to see how well they are contextualizing the theoretical knowledge they have gained in their individual businesses. The research was grounded in Kolb's theory of learning via experience (Experiential Learning Theory). Learners who have successfully completed the Work Immersion Program are among the participants. These participants include supervisors from partner universities, which can be either public or private. In order to investigate the specifics of the study, the researchers employed the Mixed method design, and in particular the sequential explanatory design. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected with the help of a structured survey questionnaire developed by the Department of Education, Region III, Division of Bulacan and semi-structured guide interview questions, respectively. These tools were utilized in order to collect the quantitative and qualitative data. The findings indicate that the supervisors of the work immersion students are pleased with the performance of the students. A SWOT analysis was used to identify gaps in the training programs, which served as the basis for the proposed training program for work immersion students. Moreover, the findings, recommendations, and implications were discussed in the study.

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